

A Simple Method for Eliminating Double Counting in Multi-Model Ensemble Forecasts

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Abstract

We describe a method for eliminating double counting in multi-model ensemble forecasts. The method involves applying weights to the individual model predictions. The weights are derived from empirically estimated correlations between the outputs from the models in the ensemble, without reference to observations. The weighted ensemble mean can then be used as an improved best-estimate forecast, and the weighted ensemble spread as an improved estimate of the model uncertainty. Additional weights could subsequently be added to reflect agreement (or not) between the ensemble members and observations.

1 Introduction

In many mathematical modelling situations predictions are dependent on somewhat arbitrary choices of model structure. This can occur with both dynamical or statistical model predictions. In dynamical model predictions it may occur in situations where models are far from converged with respect to grid resolution in space or time, or in which certain physical processes are approximated rather than being resolved. In statistical models it tends to occur when there is little data available to train the model, or when the structure of the data is complex.

As a result, various methods have been developed to attempt to quantify *model uncertainty* (which we define here as the uncertainty related to arbitrary choices of model methodology and structure). Such methods often rely on the creation of an ensemble of alternative prediction models, and combine predictions from those models together in some way.¹ The simplest approach to combining such models is to average the models in the ensemble together with equal weights on the different models. This method has no need for any training data. In cases where a large amount of training data is available, for both hindcasts from the models, and the corresponding observations, multiple linear regression can be used and may well outperform straight averaging. In between these two extremes, where a more limited amount of training data is available, some kind of bias-variance trade-off method (shrinkage regression, minimum mean-squared error regression, ridge regression) can be used.²

One issue that arises in combining multiple models is that of double counting, or partial double counting.³ Double counting occurs when two models are identical in terms of their predictions. If both models are included in an ensemble, then that prediction may be double counted in the final forecast, for no good reason other than the (most likely) arbitrary choice to include those particular models in the ensemble in the first place. Partial double counting is the weaker version of this effect that occurs when near identical, or even just slightly correlated models are included in an ensemble. Partial double counting only does not occur when model predictions are completely independent. We will refer to both partial double counting and double counting generically as double counting. Of the methods mentioned above, the regression methods take account of double counting effects, while simple model averaging does not. But, as mentioned above, regression can only be used when there is a large amount of both observational and model data. In many cases, particularly related to climate prediction, there is insufficient observational data on which to base a reliable regression, or even shrinkage regression, although there may be extensive model-only simulations.⁴

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¹See Collins (2007) for an overview of the use of ensembles of models in climate prediction.

²See DelSole et al. (2013) for a discussion of whether equal or unequal weights work better in seasonal climate forecasting.

³See, for example, comments in Tebaldi and Knutti (2007) on the topic of model dependence.

⁴See the discussion in Weigel et al. (2010).

In this paper, we describe a new method that produces weights for ensemble models that correct for double counting. The method uses model simulations but not observations, and so can be used in situations where there is insufficient observational data for regression.

The method works as follows. Correlations of model predictions are estimated between all pairs of models, and are used to construct a correlation matrix. From this correlation matrix, weights are then derived for each model. Models that are more similar to other models in the ensemble will be downweighted, while models that are less similar, or stand out as different, will be upweighted. This downweighting and upweighting is appropriate in situations in which the selection of models in the ensemble was driven by arbitrary or practical considerations, and when there is no reason to believe that the selection of models reflects anything about the true model uncertainty. Under certain somewhat idealized assumptions we show that this anti-double-counting step itself already increases the mean-square-error skill of predictions from the model ensemble, even though it involves no comparison with observations.

In section 2 we set up the mathematical framework we use to analyze this question. This leads to a constrained optimisation problem. In section 3 we solve the optimisation problem, and derive a simple equation for the weights. In section 4 we show that the resulting weights are positive in the 2 model case. In section 5 we show that the method gives weights which are invariant to the addition of an additional model, again in the 2 model case. In section 6 we then give eight examples, all based on 3 model ensembles. In seven of the examples the solutions for the weights follow intuition well. However, in example eight we get a negative weight on one model, which we do not consider sensible. In section 7 we summarize the article, discuss the negative weight issue, and describe possible future work.

2 The Mathematical Framework

We now describe the mathematical framework that we use to derive our anti-double-counting weights. We consider a set of point predictions of a scalar quantity, from a set of N models. We let:

- m_{ij} be prediction from model i for time j
- p_j be a weighted prediction for time j made by averaging the m_{ij} together in some way
- w_i be a weight for model i

We assume that the predictions m_{ij} have each been separately standardized to have mean in time of zero and variance in time of one. This is on the basis of the assumption that the useful information in the predictions is contained in the variability, not the variance.

The weighted prediction p_j is then defined as:

$$p_j = \sum_{i=1}^N m_{ij} w_i \quad (1)$$

In vector and matrix notation:

$$p = w^T m \quad (2)$$

We now let

- r_j be an observation at time j that we are trying to predict

The error between the prediction and the observation at time j is then given by:

$$e_j = p_j - r_j \quad (3)$$

and the mean squared error over all T times observed is given by:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{T} \sum_j e_j^2 = \sum_j (p_j - r_j)^2 \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \sum_j (p_j^2 - 2p_j r_j + r_j^2) \quad (5)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j p_j^2 - 2 \sum_j p_j r_j + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j p_j^2 - 2 \sum_j \sum_i m_{ij} w_i r_j + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (7)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j p_j^2 - 2 \sum_i \sum_j m_{ij} w_i r_j + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j p_j^2 - 2 \sum_i w_i \sum_j m_{ij} r_j + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (9)$$

$$= \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j p_j^2 - 2 \sum_i w_i s_i + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (10)$$

where s_i is the covariance between model i and the observations, which is a measure of the skill of the model.

We now separate the weights w_i into a mean weight \bar{w} and deviations around the mean w'_i , where $w'_i = w_i - \bar{w}$. We also separate the skill measure s_i in the same way, so that $s'_i = s_i - \bar{s}$.

We then have:

$$\sum_i w_i s_i = \sum_i (\bar{w} + w'_i)(\bar{s} + s'_i) \quad (11)$$

$$= \sum_i \bar{w} \bar{s} + \bar{w} s'_i + \bar{s} w'_i + w'_i s'_i \quad (12)$$

$$= \sum_i \bar{w} \bar{s} + \sum_i w'_i s'_i \quad (13)$$

We now assume that the weights that we apply to the models are independent of the skill of the different models. This makes sense since the weights are determined from model predictions with no reference to the observations. As a result, $\sum_i w'_i s'_i \approx 0$. We also note that $\bar{w} = \frac{1}{N}$, and so

$$\sum_i w_i s_i = \bar{s} \quad (14)$$

This gives

$$\text{MSE} \approx \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j p_j^2 - 2\bar{s} + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (15)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j \sum_i \sum_k (m_{ij} w_i)(m_{kj} w_k) - 2\bar{s} + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (16)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_j \sum_i \sum_k (m_{ij} m_{kj}) w_i w_k - 2\bar{s} + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (17)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{T} \left(\sum_i \sum_j C_{ik} w_i w_k - 2\bar{s} + \sum_j r_j^2 \right) \quad (18)$$

where we have defined C as the correlation matrix of the model predictions.

Equivalently:

$$\text{MSE} \approx \frac{1}{T} (pp^T - 2\bar{s} + r^T r) \quad (19)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{T} (w^T m m^T w - 2\bar{s} + r^T r) \quad (20)$$

$$\approx \frac{1}{T} (w^T C w - 2\bar{s} + r^T r) \quad (21)$$

We would like to minimize the MSE by varying w subject to the constraint that the weights add up to one ($\sum_i w_i = 1$). This can be done using a Lagrange multiplier λ by defining a cost function:

$$z = \sum_i \sum_j C_{ij} w_i w_j - 2\lambda \left(\sum_i w_i - 1 \right) \quad (22)$$

or

$$z = w^T C w - 2\lambda (w^T \mathbf{1} - 1) \quad (23)$$

Where $\mathbf{1}$ is a vector of ones.

Note that we have dropped the \bar{s} and $E(r_j^2)$ terms from the cost function, since they are not a function of the weights w , and that we have put an arbitrary factor of 2 in front of the Lagrange multiplier to make the algebra a little more elegant later on in the derivation of the solution.

In the next section, we consider how to minimize this cost function.

3 Solving for the Weights

Having established a framework for considering the impact of weighting the members of the forecast ensemble on the skill of the forecast, we now attempt to minimise the MSE of the ensemble mean by varying the weights.

Differentiating the cost function z by w_k gives:

$$\frac{\partial z}{\partial w_k} = \frac{\partial}{\partial w_k} \left[\sum_i \sum_j C_{ij} w_i w_j - 2\lambda \left(\sum_i w_i - 1 \right) \right] \quad (24)$$

$$= \sum_i \sum_j C_{ij} \frac{\partial}{\partial w_k} [w_i w_j] - 2\lambda \left(\sum_i \frac{\partial}{\partial w_k} [w_i] \right) \quad (25)$$

$$= \sum_i \sum_j C_{ij} (w_i \delta_{jk} + w_j \delta_{ik}) - 2\lambda \left(\sum_i \delta_{ik} \right) \quad (26)$$

$$= \sum_i C_{ik} w_i + \sum_j C_{kj} w_j - 2\lambda \quad (27)$$

$$= \sum_i C_{ki} w_i + \sum_j C_{kj} w_j - 2\lambda \quad (28)$$

$$= 2 \sum_i C_{ki} w_i - 2\lambda \quad (29)$$

In vector notation:

$$\nabla_w z = 2Cw - 2\lambda \mathbf{1} \quad (30)$$

Setting this gradient equal to zero gives:

$$2Cw = 2\lambda \mathbf{1} \quad (31)$$

$$w = \lambda C^{-1} \mathbf{1} \quad (32)$$

where we've assumed that C is invertible.

The unknown constant λ must be chosen so that $\sum_i w_i = 1$.

We let $u = C^{-1} \mathbf{1}$ and so

$$\lambda = \frac{1}{\sum_i u_i} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{1}^T u} = \frac{1}{\mathbf{1}^T C^{-1} \mathbf{1}} \quad (33)$$

What is the value of the cost function at this extremum?

Substituting into equation 23 gives:

$$z = \sum_i \sum_j D_{ij} w_i w_j - 2\lambda \left(\sum_i w_i - 1 \right) \quad (34)$$

$$= \sum_i w_i \left(\sum_j D_{ij} w_j \right) \quad (35)$$

$$= \sum_i w_i \lambda \tag{36}$$

$$= \lambda \tag{37}$$

$$= \frac{1}{1^T C^{-1} 1} \tag{38}$$

(note that $1^T C^{-1} 1$ is just the sum of the terms in C^{-1}).

3.1 Plug-in Estimation of the Weights

To estimate w in practice we might:

- Estimate C with an empirical estimate \hat{C}
- Estimate u using $\hat{u} = \hat{C}^{-1} 1$
- Estimate λ by normalising \hat{u} i.e. $\hat{\lambda} = 1 / \sum_i \hat{u}_i$
- Estimate w using $\hat{w} = \hat{\lambda} \hat{u}$

3.2 Relationship to Eigenvalue Problems

By way of interest, we note that this is not an eigenvalue problem. This is because the constraint on the weights is such that the sum of the weights is equal to 1, rather than the constraint that the sum of the *squares* of the weights is equal to 1, which does then lead to an eigenvalue problem. It may be possible to reformulate the problem as an eigenvalue problem in some way: we have not explored that possibility in detail.

3.3 Relationship to Linear Regression

We note that the weights derived above are in fact a special case of the weights that would come from linear regression of the observations onto the models, for the situation in which the correlations between the models and the observations are assumed constant (the same for all models).

3.4 Relationship to Bayesian Statistics

The whole method proposed is analogous to Bayesian statistics in that the weights derived above could be used to form an objective prior, and could then be updated by comparison with observations. This analogy becomes more literal in the probabilistic extension, which we have not considered in this paper.

4 Proof of Non-negativity of the Weights in the 2x2 Case

We now show that the resulting weights are non-negative in the 2 model case.

With 2 models:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b \\ b & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad C^{-1} = \frac{1}{1-b^2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -b \\ -b & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \left(\frac{1}{1-b^2} \right) \begin{pmatrix} 1-b \\ 1-b \end{pmatrix} \tag{39}$$

Since b is a correlation coefficient, $-1 \leq b \leq 1$, and so $0 \leq 1-b \leq 2$.

We note that using a covariance matrix rather than a correlation matrix would not have this property of giving non-negative weights, even in this 2 model case.

5 Proof of Invariance to Additional Models

We now show that the weights are invariant to the addition of a duplicate model, in the 2 model case. We cannot do this by adding a precisely duplicate model and then recalculating the weights, since the correlation matrix C becomes non-invertible. Instead we consider a third model that tends towards the second model. We show that, as it does so, the weights tend towards the original weights.

For two models:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b \\ b & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad C^{-1} = \frac{1}{1-b^2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -b \\ -b & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \left(\frac{1}{1-b^2} \right) \begin{pmatrix} 1-b \\ 1-b \end{pmatrix} \tag{40}$$

We now consider adding a third model which is highly correlated with model 2, which gives:

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & b & b \\ b & 1 & d \\ b & d & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad C^{-1} = \frac{1}{1 - d^2 + 2b^2d - 2b^2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 - d^2 & bd - b & bd - b \\ bd - b & 1 - b^2 & b^2 - d \\ bd - b & b^2 - d & 1 - b^2 \end{pmatrix} \quad (41)$$

and

$$w = \left(\frac{1}{1 - d^2 + 2b^2d - 2b^2} \right) \begin{pmatrix} 1 - d^2 - 2b + 2bd \\ 1 - d - b + bd \\ 1 - d - b + bd \end{pmatrix} \quad (42)$$

We now let d tend towards 1, so that the third model tends towards being a duplicate of the second model. We let $\epsilon = 1 - d$ so that $d = 1 - \epsilon$. Then $d^2 = (1 - \epsilon)^2 \approx (1 - 2\epsilon)$, and $1 - d^2 \approx 2\epsilon$.

Given this:

$$w \approx \left(\frac{1}{2\epsilon - 2b^2\epsilon} \right) \begin{pmatrix} 2\epsilon - 2b\epsilon \\ \epsilon - b\epsilon \\ \epsilon - b\epsilon \end{pmatrix} = \left(\frac{1}{2\epsilon(1 - b^2)} \right) \begin{pmatrix} 2\epsilon(1 - b) \\ \epsilon(1 - b) \\ \epsilon(1 - b) \end{pmatrix} = \left(\frac{1}{1 - b^2} \right) \begin{pmatrix} (1 - b) \\ \frac{1}{2}(1 - b) \\ \frac{1}{2}(1 - b) \end{pmatrix} \quad (43)$$

and we can see that the weights tend towards the same as in the original two model case, but with the weight on model 2 now split over models 2 and 3, thus giving the same predictions.

6 Examples

Having derived a simple equation (equation 32) for the optimal weights, we now consider various numerical examples. In each case, we start with a 3x3 correlation matrix C , and derive the weights for that matrix. We also give the ratio of the value of the cost function achieved at the minimum to the value of the cost function that would be achieved with flat weights (as a percentage).

6.1 Example 1

Our first example is a sanity test in which we assume that the 3 predictions are independent. In this case, the reweighting has no effect, relative to flat weights.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.333 \\ 0.333 \\ 0.333 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 1.0 \quad (44)$$

6.2 Example 2

In our second example we introduce a small correlation between predictions 1 and 2. As expected, this results in slightly lower weights for those two predictions relative to prediction 3. The cost function also reduces, as expected.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.25 & 0 \\ 0.25 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.308 \\ 0.308 \\ 0.385 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 98.9 \quad (45)$$

6.3 Example 3

In this example, we increase the correlation between predictions 1 and 2. The impact on the weights and the cost function is then greater than in example 1.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.5 & 0 \\ 0.5 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.286 \\ 0.286 \\ 0.429 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 96.4 \quad (46)$$

6.4 Example 4

We now set the correlation between the predictions 1 and 2 very close to 1. As expected, the weight on prediction 3 is nearly double the weights on predictions 1 and 2. The cost function also reduces materially in this case.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.99 & 0 \\ 0.99 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.251 \\ 0.251 \\ 0.499 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 90.1 \quad (47)$$

6.5 Example 5

In this example we make the 3 predictions positively and equally correlated. As expected, the weights come out as equal, and there is no improvement in the score.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.5 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 1 & 0.5 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.333 \\ 0.333 \\ 0.333 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 100.0 \quad (48)$$

6.6 Example 6

In this example, prediction 1 is fairly highly correlated with prediction 2, prediction 1 is somewhat correlated with prediction 3, and predictions 2 and 3 are only weakly correlated. Weight 1 ends up lowest, since prediction 1 is the least unique. Conversely, weight 3 ends up the highest since prediction 3 is the most unique.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.5 & 0.25 \\ 0.5 & 1 & 0.125 \\ 0.25 & 0.125 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.241 \\ 0.345 \\ 0.414 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 98.0 \quad (49)$$

6.7 Example 7

In this example, predictions 1 and 2 are negatively correlated with each other, and uncorrelated with prediction 3. This results in higher weights on predictions 1 and 2 than on 3.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -0.25 & 0 \\ -0.25 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} 0.364 \\ 0.364 \\ 0.273 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 98.1 \quad (50)$$

6.8 Example 8

Our final example is similar to example 6, in which predictions 1 and 2 are strongly correlated, 1 and 3 are less correlated, and 2 and 3 are only weakly correlated. This now results in negative weights on model 1.

$$C = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0.8 & 0.5 \\ 0.8 & 1 & 0.2 \\ 0.5 & 0.2 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad w = \begin{pmatrix} -0.205 \\ 0.641 \\ 0.564 \end{pmatrix}, \quad z_{\min}/z_0 = 88.5 \quad (51)$$

7 Summary

We have considered the question of how to merge point predictions from a multi-model ensemble. We have derived an expression for weights that attempt to reduce the sum of squared errors of the final weighted average prediction by adjusting weights on the forecasts and reducing double counting. The weights are based on an estimated correlation matrix, and we have given some examples of 3x3 correlation matrices and the weights that result from them. The first seven examples show intuitively sensible behaviour, with the highest weights on the most unique predictions, and the lowest weights on the most correlated predictions. They also show that, when the models are not either completely correlated or uncorrelated, there is a reduction in the associated MSE. The percentage reductions in the MSE would likely be larger for larger model ensembles. Example eight, however, gives negative weights for one of the models. We consider this non-ideal, since it seems intuitively not sensible to use one model just to cancel out the effect of other models.

This study number raises a number of questions, and avenues for future work, as listed below.

- We have considered point forecasts. It would be useful to generalize the above framework to probabilistic forecasts. That is our next plan.
- We have proposed using a plug-in estimator for the correlation matrix. In practice, especially for small training data-sets, the correlation matrix may be poorly estimated. As a result it may be worth considering the entire posterior distribution of the correlation matrix, or shrinking the correlation matrix towards the identity. It may also be possible in extreme cases that estimation error kills the entire endeavour, and that using flat weights would give better predictions. It would be useful to derive methods for the shrinkage, and rules to decide which strategy to use.
- We have been able to show that the weights are always positive in the 2 model case, but example eight shows that this is not true for more than two models. It is possible that the negative weight issue could be eliminated, perhaps by solving a constrained optimisation algorithm with the constraint that the weights cannot be negative. This would, however, be slightly more involved.
- We have been able to show that the weights are invariant to the addition of a duplicate model, but again only in the 2 model case. We *think* that they will always be invariant to the addition of duplicate models, for any number of models, but have not shown that.
- And finally, it would be interesting to apply this method to some actual prediction data to test it.

8 Acknowledgements and Comments

The author would like to thank Dan Rowlands for interesting discussions on this topic.

We also note that, just prior to publication, we became aware that T. Mendlik, M. Collins and B. Bhaskaran are working on a similar method. We have not had the opportunity to compare the methods in detail and at this point we are unsure if the methods are merely similar, or exactly the same.

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